

Paper 17

NATIONAL ACADEMIC CREDIT BANK – A GLOBAL PERSPECTIVE

Keerthan Raj & Dr. P.S.Aithal

College of Management & Commerce, Srinivas University, Pandeshwar, Mangalore - 575
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2keerthanraj@gmail.com

Abstract

The higher education in India is poised on an agenda of change towards the movement from Credit Based Choice System (CBCS) to National Academic Credit Bank (NACB) as proposed by the UGC. If the Union government is able to formulate a policy, this will mark the beginning of a new phase in the Indian Higher Education System. This would allow the students to pursue their higher education from different universities and earn a degree from another university. Credit transfers are prevalent in many countries and its success is ensured by the creation of an online repository of students looking for potential credit transfer opportunities. Though it requires a vast amount of ground work and pathways created, once implemented, the NAC Bank would help students plan their objectives and their pace. This paper we study the modus operandi as the scheme and its existence in different countries and its implications on the student fraternity.

Keywords: Academic, credit, transfers, online

1. Introduction

Technological advances in fields of communication and transportation have increased educational opportunities for post-secondary education students across the globe. Individuals as well as information now travels quicker and cheaper between countries and continents. The institutions offering post-secondary education no longer have a local, jurisdictional or even domestic focus; their vision is global. In spite of India developing a lot of higher educational institutions we are not on a global list of students aspiring to come to study in India and academic credit transfers could also be one of the lacuna that is seen. In addition the advantages add to, governments and employers recognizing that the workforce of the future must well-trained, globally aware professionals with international work experience who can solve economic and social problems. At the same time, students and faculty are becoming increasingly interested in spending time in different academic environments, often in foreign surroundings. The length of stay amongst these programs can range from one semester to the pursuit of a full academic credential. If there is a mechanism or a proper procedure that is designed to recognize previous academic performance, this would ensure that a full range of student mobility is created. It is for this reason that credit transfer and student mobility are linked. Credit transfer systems provide the lubricant to ensure seamless academic mobility.

Understanding the academic credit system?

An academic credit system is a standard used by universities to measure and assess students' work and effort during their programme. It's important to understand how credits work and how credit points from one academic system are converted to credits from other credit systems, if possible. Sometimes students need to take preparation courses in order to meet starting credit requirements needed for university admission. Academic credit transfer systems offer the following advantages to the institutions and nations offering the same -

- Facilitate inter institutional cooperation - there is greater inter institutional cooperation amongst the various universities/institutions at conjoint with each other.
- Student mobility - It facilitates greater student mobility between nations which also paves the way for fostering economic growth.
- Enhance quality of higher education
- Increase global competitiveness – The curriculums will be designed at global standards, increasing the standards of education
- Establish a standard for quality assurance and accreditation - It sets standards for quality assurance amongst institutions.

2. International Credit Systems – Some of the most relevant academic credits for international students are:

a. **ECTS - European credits** -The European Credit Transfer and Accumulation System (ECTS) is a tool of the European Higher Education System for making studies and courses more transparent. It helps students to move between countries and to have their academic qualifications and study periods abroad recognised. ECTS allows credits taken at one higher education institution to be counted towards a qualification studied for at another. ECTS credits represent learning based on defined learning outcomes and their associated workload. ECTS enhances the flexibility of study programmes for students. It also supports the planning, delivery and evaluation of higher education programmes. European Credit Transfer and Accumulation System (ECTS) credits are a standard means for comparing the "volume of learning based on the defined learning outcomes and their associated workload" for higher education across the European union and other collaborating European countries. For successfully completed studies, ECTS credits are awarded. One academic year corresponds to 60 ECTS credits that are normally equivalent to 1500–1800 hours of total workload, irrespective of standard or qualification type. ECTS credits are used to facilitate transfer and progression throughout the Union. ECTS also includes a standard grading scale intended to be shown in addition to local.

For each course a person takes during the degree studies, they will earn a number of credits. Assessment are done in terms of the amount of knowledge and skills that is achieved once the course is completed. Common forms of assessment are a combination of:

- actual attendance

- tests taken during the course
- projects/research work
- oral/written examination

Mainly, each course is worth a certain number of credit points, determined by different criteria including student's workload, learning outcome and contact hours. Usually, the more work and effort a student is required to put into a course, the more credits that course is worth.

b. Academic credit systems in Australia

Australian universities do not have a unified credit system. Each university in Australia calculates the credits according to workload and number of study hours per each course.

Credit transfer is available for both undergraduate and postgraduate study programmes and it is established and coordinated by the Australian Qualifications Framework.

Universities in Australia (as well as individual faculties or departments in a university) have different rules regarding independent study and transfer credit.

In Australian universities, each subject usually has a value between 6 and 8, but there may be some exceptions and find credit points below or over this average. Normally, during a semester, you would study 4 subjects. Each university may decide how many subjects students are allowed to choose for each semester.

According to the academic credit system in Australia, Bachelor degrees require completion of 144 credit points (for 3 years Bachelor degrees) and for completing a postgraduate degree, you would need 96 credits. Credit assessment may take up to three months and costs vary depending on the number of qualifications assessed. Students may apply for assessment online. A number of credits are awarded as a result of the assessment process. Universities decide if the student meets their academic requirements after evaluating the results of the assessment.

c. Academic credit systems in the U.S.

In the U.S., students receive semester credit hours, which are based on the number of contact hours accumulated during one semester. Mainly, a student would have to take around 5 courses each semester, where each course is worth 3 semester credit hours, the equivalent of 45-48 contact hours. All these would add up to 30 credits per year, the required number to successfully complete a degree in the U.S.

d. Korea's Academic Credit Bank System

This has been the most widely appreciated and well regarded academic credit transfer system in the world, the Academic Credit Bank system (ACBS) is an open educational system which recognizes diverse learning experiences gained not only in-school but also out-of school. When the learner accumulates the necessary ACBS-approved credits, he/she can be awarded a degree. The Academic Credit Bank System, a central agency for continuing education, aims to provide all citizens with greater access to a variety of educational opportunities and to foster a lifelong learning society. This program aims at

innovating, diversifying and maximizing the educational opportunities for both students, studying at post-secondary institutes, and adults, seeking additional education and training. This is a unique system where credits are given for job periods as well, hence benefitting adults as well.

The ACBS is intended to benefit the following groups:

- Students and adults who could not continue their education.
- High school graduates who were previously unable to attend post-secondary institutes.
- Workers who hold professional certificates but did not acquire a university degree.
- College or university graduates who wish to commence studies in a different field.
- People who wish to acquire formal credits for knowledge and skills gained through self-instruction and workplace training and experience.
- People who have studied at private institutes or junior colleges and wish to transfer into the university system.

Credits are acquired primarily through education and job training institutes, part-time enrollment, certificate acquisition, and passing the Bachelor's Degree Examination program for self-education. The ACBS also grants recognition to a learner's diverse learning experiences, including prior course credits and various forms of learning.

Educational institutes are formally evaluated to be an ACBS-accredited institute offering courses which can be counted as university or college equivalent credits.

The Ministry of Education, Science and Technology (MEST), the National Institute for Lifelong Education (NILE), and Provincial Offices of Education are involved in the administration of the Credit Bank. The Korean academic credit model is very well studied and the model has been adopted by several countries.

3. The major benefits of the academic credit transfer systems are analysed and put forth herewith-

- Credits support your entry to a higher education programme
- They keep track of student progress and determine when he/she has met study requirements
- They estimate the workload of a programme
- You can transfer to another university programme while keeping part or all previously earned credit points
- Use the credit you earned to study abroad – academic credit is used and recognised internationally
- Academic credits act as proof of previous studies when looking for a job
- Some universities use academic study credits to set degree costs

The advantages of the academic credit system are various in terms of giving better opportunities to students to garner the requisite skills to pursue further studies and combine the pursuit of education with academic goals. Even institutions benefit by developing a very good academic standards and having best in class students pursuing education.

4. **Strategies Used to Maintain Academic Standards** – In India, as envisaged if the academic credit transfer system has to be a successful model, lot of learnings from the existing credit transfer models have to be adopted and it is imperative that the strategies mentioned herein has to be adopted for the success of the model. In the first instance, the national adoption of a consistent education profile is a necessary prerequisite for effective credit transfer system in place, there needs to be a monitoring authority to govern the credit transfers and institutional set up. Simultaneously, the organizational policies and procedures should make it conducive to accreditation and building a national policy.

Strategies	Necessary Conditions
National adoption of a consistent education profile	Credit transfer between education providers needs to have a monitoring and governing body
Organizational accreditation or national recognition of education provider Program accreditation/approval process	Helps to verify a bonafide education provider Institutional committee to peer review internal standards Professional/industry bodies to ensure curriculum enables desired educational outcome
Organizational policies and processes to recognize prior learning and number of credit transfers acceptable for any degree program, conditions and circumstances	Overall organizational policy determining acceptable standards (viz., not more than 50% of credits obtained at another education provider to be recognized)
Quality assurance framework	Establishing min acceptable non disputable scores (eg., IELTS) pertaining to Indian requirements

The strategic advantages far outweigh the disadvantages associated with the gradual motion to a credit transfer system, this foresees enormous benefits for the society and the broader education scheme as a whole, it definitely has far-reaching impacts and will be a move in the correct direction for the Indian greater education system.

5. Conclusion

The Indian higher education system though very vibrant, poised for growth and expansive still has very large scope for improvement. Even if we were to compare the Indian education system with global educators, we see a dearth wherein Indian institutions are not

figured amongst the top rated in the world. Through a movement to the national credit transfer system there will definitely be a possibility of being one amongst the globally recognized portals of higher education.

6. References

[1] Altbach, P. G. (2001). Measuring academic progress: the course-credit system in American Higher Education, *Higher Education Policy*, 14(1), 37-44.

[2] ERASMUS, <https://ec.europa.eu> website accessed on 21st July, 2019.

[3] Usher, A. (2014). *The Korean Academic Credit Bank: A Model for Credit Transfer in North America?* Toronto: Higher Education Strategy Associates